

Structural Model of Effective Factors on Risk Appetite: A Grounded Theory Paradigm

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ABSTRACT

Adhering to risk appetites through their formulation guarantees that risk management stays in line with predefined levels of risk, even though accepted banks can frequently tolerate higher levels of risk. In light of the aforementioned, the primary goal of the current study is to examine, create, and validate a structural model of the variables affecting the risk appetites of recognised banks on the stock exchange using the grounded theory paradigm. Data was collected through semi-structured interviews with 15 accounting experts using snowball sampling and theoretical sampling. After using Grounded Theory paradigm suggested by Strauss and Corbin (1990) to design and validate structural model factors that have influence on risk appetite in banks listed on stock exchange, based on our qualitative analysis we design a new structural model using four new factors that have influence on risk appetite in banks listed on stock exchange, which are: (1) causal conditions (organizational factors, organizational maturity); (2) intervening conditions (communication expansion); (3) intervening strategies (risk management methods), and (4) outcomes (organizational growth, continuity of activities). We validated our new structural model using confirmatory and discriminant analysis methods, while reliability was assessed through repeatability and generalizability. This finding will help banks to determine what kind of risk appetites investors have.

ملخص

الالتزام بالرغبة في المخاطرة من خلال صياغتها يضمن تماشي عملية إدارة المخاطر مع مستويات المخاطر المحددة مسبقاً، على الرغم من أن البنوك المعترف بها يمكنها في كثير من الأحيان تحمل

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مستويات أعلى من المخاطر. وفي ظل ما سبق، يتمثل الهدف الأساسي من هذه الدراسة في تفحص وإنشاء واختبار صحة نموذج هيكلي للمتغيرات التي تؤثر على إقبال البنوك المعترف بها على المخاطرة في البورصة باستخدام نموذج نظرية التفاعل الحقلية. وجمعت البيانات من خلال مقابلات شبه منظمة مع 15 خبيراً في المحاسبة عن طريق جمع العينات بأسلوب كرة الثلج والعيّنات النظرية. بعد استخدام نموذج نظرية التفاعل الحقلية، الذي اقترحه ستراوس وكوربين (Strauss and Corbin, 1990) لتصميم نموذج هيكلي للعوامل المؤثرة على الرغبة في المخاطرة في البنوك المدرجة في البورصة والتحقق منه، واستناداً إلى تحليلنا النوعي، صممنا نموذجاً هيكلياً جديداً باعتماد أربعة عوامل جديدة لها تأثير على الرغبة في المخاطرة في البنوك المدرجة في البورصة، وهي: (1) الظروف السببية (العوامل التنظيمية، النضج التنظيمي)، و(2) الظروف المتداخلة (التوسع في التواصل)، و(3) الاستراتيجيات المتداخلة (أساليب إدارة المخاطر)، و(4) النتائج (النمو التنظيمي، استمرارية الأنشطة). وتحققنا من صحة نموذجنا الهيكلي الجديد باستخدام أساليب التحليل التأكدي والتمييزي، في حين تم تقييم الموثوقية من خلال قابلية التكرار والتعميم. من شأن النتيجة المتوصل إليها أن تساعد البنوك في تحديد نوع الإقبال على المخاطرة في صفوف المستثمرين.

RESUME

Le respect de l'appétit pour le risque par sa formulation garantit que la gestion du risque reste conforme aux niveaux de risque prédéfinis, même si les banques reconnues peuvent fréquemment tolérer des niveaux de risque plus élevés. À la lumière de ce qui précède, l'objectif principal de la présente étude est d'examiner, de créer et de valider un modèle structurel des variables affectant l'appétit pour le risque des banques reconnues en bourse en utilisant le paradigme de la théorie ancrée. Les données ont été collectées au moyen d'entretiens semi-structurés avec 15 experts comptables en utilisant un échantillonnage en boule de neige et un échantillonnage théorique. Après avoir utilisé le paradigme de la théorie ancrée suggéré par Strauss et Corbin (1990) pour concevoir et valider les facteurs du modèle structurel qui ont une influence sur l'appétit pour le risque dans les banques cotées en bourse, nous avons conçu, sur la base de notre analyse qualitative, un nouveau modèle structurel utilisant quatre nouveaux facteurs qui ont une influence sur l'appétit pour le risque dans les banques cotées en bourse, qui sont : (1) conditions causales (facteurs organisationnels, maturité organisationnelle) ; (2) conditions d'intervention (expansion de la communication) ; (3) stratégies d'intervention (méthodes de gestion des risques), et (4) résultats (croissance organisationnelle, continuité des activités). Nous avons validé notre nouveau modèle structurel à l'aide de méthodes d'analyse confirmatoire et discriminante, tandis que la fiabilité a été évaluée par la

répétabilité et la généralisabilité. Ces résultats aideront les banques à déterminer le type d'appétit pour le risque des investisseurs.

Keywords: Risk Management; Risk Appetite; Structural model; Grounded Theory Paradigm.

JEL Classification: E12; E43; E52

1. Introduction

Risk appetite reflects the level of risk that a bank is willing to accept to achieve its business objectives. Fundamental risks include credit risk, liquidity risk, operational risks, market risks (including interest rate and currency exchange rate risks), and reputation risk. The risk appetite framework imposes constraints based on capital adequacy, liquidity adequacy, and concentration risks, with the ultimate goal of reducing income volatility, ensuring a strong capital and liquidity structure in economic cycles, and maintaining the bank's reputation (Kayani & Hasan, 2024; Yari et al., 2021).

Risk appetite is annually reviewed by the board of directors with the assistance of the risk management unit, and its implementation is the responsibility of the board. Since the risk phenomenon is inherent, businesses strive to create processes, methods, and tools for logical risk management, maintaining it at acceptable levels in line with organizational goals. Despite the not being a new concept in financial literature, recent financial crises and their profound effects on the bankruptcy of companies and financial institutions, particularly banks, underscore its increasing importance (Soleimani et al., 2020). The accepted amount of risk must be determined by the organization based on market conditions, and most importantly, the tolerable level of risk (Yari et al., 2021).

Risk appetite forms the core of a comprehensive risk management solution and serves as a metric for comparing the overall risk status within the organization. The primary goal of risk management is to maximize shareholder value. Internal controls are weaker for more complex companies; therefore, unified risk management for a business unit should theoretically offer more benefits (Hosseini et al., 2022). Studies indicate

that, to the extent that management is more capable in expanding and implementing risk appetite documents in various areas of the company, more activities are covered by the risk management process. Processes and more sections of the company are involved in prevention and coping with risks (Yari et al., 2021). In companies where management has the necessary ability regarding the design and use of processes and risk appetite documents in various activities, the level of company risk has significantly decreased. In contrast, in companies where necessary actions have not been taken regarding the design of risk appetite processes and the use of risk appetite documents in various areas of company activities, they face more challenges in managing risks related to the continuity of operations.

Companies develop their strategies based on risks and business environment opportunities. They periodically revise their strategies in line with environmental changes to reduce risks as much as possible and utilize opportunities to create value in the company (Ullah et al., 2022). To achieve this, management must have the ability to use appropriate frameworks to optimize company strategies and performance. In this regard, companies whose managers could establish an integrated risk management framework or key areas such as risk appetite documents are more successful in achieving company goals (Hasan et al., 2022). Risk appetite at the board level is the amount of risk the organization is willing to accept to create value. The organization's risk appetite, aligned with strategy and budget documents, contributes to the coherence of organizational activities to achieve the goals set in these documents (De Zwart., 2022).

One of the fundamental problems faced by accepted banks in the stock market is the inconsistency between the risks banks encounter and the risks that the board of directors is aware of. This issue is crucial, requiring the board of directors and the CEO to have a precise understanding of risk appetites and to be well-acquainted with the risks they are willing to tolerate for profitability. In other words, management and the board of directors must proactively understand the capacity of accepted banks in the stock market to tolerate risks and accurately assess the level of tolerable risk in current and future conditions to reach the desired capacity effectively (Hasan and Al-Najjar, 2024a, 20024b).

This matter is essentially addressed by the risk appetite framework for banks, providing information to the board of directors so that they can make informative and effective decisions. Establishing risk appetites significantly aids in the continuity of managing the activities of accepted banks in the stock market at a predetermined level of activities. What is crucial is recognizing, in accepted banks in the stock market, that the selection of strategies and objectives is contingent upon understanding risk appetites. While accepted banks can often tolerate more risk, adhering to risk appetites through the formulation of risk appetites ensures that risk management remains aligned with predetermined levels of risks. Therefore, considering the above, the main objective of the current research is to investigate, develop, and validate the structural model of factors influencing the risk appetites of accepted banks in the stock exchange based on the paradigm of the grand theory. So, the fundamental question of this research is how is the structural model of factors influencing the risk appetites of accepted banks in the stock exchange? To answer this question, we conducted our research using quantitative research methods and collected our data through semi-structured interviews with 15 accounting experts using snowball sampling (first step) and theoretical sampling (second step).

After using Grounded Theory paradigm suggested by Strauss and Corbin (1990) to design and validate structural model factors that have influence on risk appetite in banks listed on stock exchange, based on our qualitative analysis we design a new structural model using four new factors that have influence on risk appetite in banks listed on stock exchange, which are: (1) causal conditions (organizational factors, organizational maturity); (2) intervening conditions (communication expansion); (3) intervening strategies (risk management methods), and (4) outcomes (organizational growth, continuity of activities). We validated our new structural model using confirmatory and discriminant analysis methods, while reliability was assessed through repeatability and generalizability.

Our findings are contributing to current literature in two different ways: firstly, we design a completely new structural model using four new factors that have influence on risk appetite in banks listed on stock exchange. Secondly, our new structural model is validated using two different (confirmatory and discriminant) analysis methods.

The rest of the paper is organised as follows. In section 2 we have provided our literature review. Methodology is provided in section 3. In section 4 we provided our findings and in section 5 model validation. In Section 6 we discussed our findings and model validation. We conclude our paper in section 7.

2. Literature Review

In this research paper we investigated, created, and validated a structural model of the variables affecting the risk appetites of recognised banks on the stock exchange using the grounded theory paradigm. To conduct this research, we first reviewed our research theoretical background, to that we explained how grounded theory works and how this is related with our research. After that we tried to establish a relationship between grounded theory and risk appetite model. In the following section we analysis previous relevant literature. In the final two sections we created a risk appetite model framework and discussed the risk appetite process.

2.1 Review of Theoretical Background

Expansion of the conceptual space of risk and risk management: Although there are differences in how risk is defined, the following brief definition illustrates its essence: risk means the probability of incurring a loss. This definition encompasses two main aspects of risk: The amount of loss must be possible and Uncertainty about that loss must also exist (Dorofee, 2018). Therefore, risk is applied to situations where the returns can be associated with imagined probability distributions. In other words, risk is the probability of the actual return rate being different from the expected return rate for an investor (Kavyani, 2017). According to the definition of risk, risk management is a process in which an individual tries to ensure that the risk they face is the same risk they think or want to deal with in guiding affairs in their preferred direction (Zarrin, 2016). Risk management, as one of the solutions for companies to deal with uncertainty in the business environment, plays an effective role in preserving and improving efficiency and effectiveness, and consequently, improving the performance of the company (Arefmanesh, 2022). The goal of risk management is to control the adverse consequences of risk tolerance and ensure the achievement of the benefits of accepting risk. This requires identifying risk and making intelligent decisions to manage it (Demirchi, 2017). Risk management enables a company to better

manage its common risks, thereby increasing the likelihood of success and reducing the likelihood of failure and uncertainty in achieving organizational goals (Li et al., 2022).

Concept and Role of Risk Appetite Terms such as risk appetite, risk fluctuation, risk management philosophy, and risk culture are important and innovative topics that have been examined in the Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) model by Kuzu (Posch, 2020).

In comparison to traditional risk management, which attempts to manage each risk on its own path and separately from the process of managing other risks, Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) examines the set of a company's risks together in a comprehensive and integrated manner (Lawson et al., 2017). This risk management approach is considered part of the overall business strategy, and one of its main goals is to increase shareholder value (Posch, 2020).

Kuzu's main philosophy, in formulating the ERM framework, is based on the idea that the value derived from a company's activities is maximized when a set of strategies is employed to achieve a desirable balance between returns and associated risks. It aims to efficiently and effectively use organizational resources to achieve goals (Posch, 2020). Risk appetite and risk tolerance levels are vital components for the effective implementation of an organization's risk management plan (Posch, 2020). Kuzu has recently provided new guidelines on how companies can improve their decision-making by specifying and formulating risk appetites (Gong, 2021), which is especially crucial in today's uncertain and complex markets.

2.2 How to use Grounded theory for Risk appetite Model

In the last two decades, different styles of grounded theory have been introduced, to the extent that they are referred to as the family of grounded theory. As a result of the development of the foundational theory, it can be considered more than a research method, a kind of perspective for researchers.

It is worth mentioning that in the process of foundation theory, data collection and their analysis, two processes are connected. Often, in this

way, data is collected through interviews and coded and analyzed through operational guidelines to produce the final theory. In this approach, primary data is provided through interviews, and data is selected and collected in different ways using theoretical sampling to complete the emerging theory. During the research process, data collection continues until theoretical saturation is reached. This means when the circular process of collecting, sorting and analyzing data and improving the theory by using them reached the point that the new data did not change the generated theory, theoretical saturation was achieved and thus, from the collection of samples New will be withheld.

2.3 Review of Empirical Background

Yari et al. (2021) investigated risk appetites, continuity risk, and the management's ability and responsiveness. The results showed that as management becomes more adept at expanding and deploying risk appetite documents in various areas of the company, more activities are covered by the risk management process. Processes and more sections of the company are involved in preventing and dealing with continuity risks.

Soleimani (2020) conducted a comparative study of the risk appetite framework in the banking industry and Iranian banks. The results indicated that risk appetites form the core of a comprehensive risk management solution and serve as a criterion for comparing the overall risk situation in the organization.

Gharahkhani (2017) examined the presentation of a risk appetite framework as a tool for determining tolerance limits for risk in insurance institutions. The results emphasized the importance of accurately determining risk appetites or risk tolerance levels, as failure to do so may lead to significant losses and, ultimately, bankruptcy.

Rezaei et al. (2020) explored the relationship between management capability and the components of integrated risk management. The results showed a positive and significant impact of management capability on integrated risk management, particularly on operational risk management.

Khosraviani and Heidarpour (2022) examined the efficiency of artificial neural networks in predicting liquidity risk for all government banks. The

study demonstrated that using accounting information and a designed neural network, it is possible to predict liquidity risk in government banks.

Rahman et al. (2020) showed that intelligence and educational background are key indicators in determining the level of management capability. Competent managers demonstrated better performance in defining risk appetites and managing higher level risks compared to other managers.

Baker and Wurgler (2002) indicated that management capability in determining appropriate levels of risk appetites corresponding to environmental conditions leads to a reduction in continuity risk. Competent managers, by understanding environmental conditions, reduced the continuity risk of company operations.

Mio et al. (2022) investigated the relationships between bank risk appetites and risk-taking, emphasizing the key role of integrated reports. The study showed that banks demonstrating higher risk-taking also provide more disclosure. Risk-taking, regardless of the area in which banks operate, acts as a mediator between adopting a specific type of report—integrated reports—and disclosing risk appetites.

Fatou et al. (2022) evaluated the relationship between risk appetites, competition, and uncertainty. The results indicated that competition and uncertainty have a strong positive effect on risk behavior, and higher economic fluctuations strengthen the potential impact of convertible bond issues on risk appetites.

Taki et al. (2021) examined the effects of risk appetites and social pressure on aggressive financial reporting behavior. The results demonstrated that the interaction between organizational risk-taking and social pressure did not affect the tendency of financial managers to engage in aggressive financial reporting.

Akdag et al. (2020) investigated the effects of fluctuations among risk appetite indicators. The results of this study revealed a unidirectional relationship, indicating that fluctuations are moving towards risk appetite indicators. This causation is observed separately in the short, medium, and long term.

Mare (2019) explored the principles of an operational risk appetite framework for a bank in South Africa. The results showed that most identified principles for an operational risk appetite framework for a South African bank are considered important and vital, although some have not been fully implemented.

Fettahoğlu (2019) examined the relationship between credit default swap premiums, credit risk appetites, and risk appetites. The study revealed that there is a significant and negative correlation between the risk appetite index and credit default swap premiums for both foreign and domestic investors.

2.4 Risk Appetite Framework

The risk appetite framework is an approach that includes policies, processes, controls, systems, and procedures, statements, risk appetites, risk limits, and roles and responsibilities statements for individuals overseeing the implementation and monitoring of the risk appetite framework. The development and formulation of the risk appetite framework are iterative and evolutionary processes. The risk appetite framework includes processes for formulating strategies, developing business plans, and models and systems for measuring and aggregating risks, which should be able to consider risk capacity, risk appetites, risk limits, and risk profiles for business units and relevant legal entities, as well as interactions with legal entities (Gharekhani, 2016). There are three key elements in a framework for setting risk appetite statements:

1. Expressing risks that are acceptable or based on strategy and that the organization intends to accept, as accepted risks are appropriately compensated. Risk tolerance levels and boundary structures, i.e., exposure limits and concentration limits, are determined for these risks.
2. Starting risks that are unacceptable or outside the strategy should be avoided, and a zero/minimal tolerance level should be set for them. These are risks that the board of directors and senior management have no appetite to accept (e.g., minimum standards for employing external employees and agents, no appetite for investing in specific high-risk countries).
3. Defining strategic, financial, and operational parameters to enable the development of a framework within which the company's business model is implemented. Parameters may be

expressed as objectives, scopes, minimums, and maximums and provide a basis for formulating risk tolerance levels and boundary structures. These parameters include strategic risk parameters (e.g., pursuing new products, leasing programs, and merger and acquisition activities), financial risk parameters (e.g., maximum acceptable loss level or performance change, including profit volatility per share, asset returns, or return on investment), and operational risk parameters.

In addition, ISO 73 Guide 2009 notes that stakeholders also have a "willingness to tolerate risk" (Gong et al., 2021). Usually, strategies and objectives derived from the risk management attitude of the organization and its board of directors, other internal and external stakeholders have different attitudes toward the level or amount of risk that the organization should accept. Recognizing the different risk attitudes of internal and external stakeholders can affect how the organization balances its risk appetite statements with the expectations of these stakeholders. When setting risk appetites, the interests of other relevant parties in achieving the company's goals should also be considered, as the goals of a company are directly related to meeting the needs and expectations of various stakeholders (such as shareholders, insurers) (Gharekhani, 2017).

2.5 Risk Appetite Process

One of the main stages of implementing organizational risk management is determining risk appetite. A company must define its position regarding risk in a risk appetite statement. An organization with aggressive risk appetites can set aggressive goals, while an organization with risk-averse appetites may set conservative goals with minimal appetite for risk. Additionally, different appetites should exist for each area of the business (Bekaert et al., 2022).

The resources used in determining risk appetites include financial capability criteria, business strategic plans, profitability, stress scenarios, risk monitoring reports, liquidity profiles, multi-year budgets, events, risk appetite strategies for other companies, damages, credit rating assessments, customer types, market growth and trends, market share objectives, and competitive outlooks. The stages of determining the risk appetite framework are in Figure 1 (Gharekhani, 2015):

Figure 1: Risk Appetite Process (Gharekhani, 2016)

3. Methodology

The current research is exploratory in nature, applied in terms of research type, and qualitative in terms of research strategy, following a foundational data theory paradigm based on the Strauss and Corbin (1990) paradigmatic model. This method employs a systematic series of procedures to generate a theory based on an understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. The research findings encompass theoretical adjustment and the reality under examination, rather than a set of interconnected figures or information. The primary goal of foundational data theory is to construct and present a theory that is truthful and enlightening in the field studied. This research strategy is anchored on three elements: concepts, categories, and propositions. The main objective is to move from the particular to the whole without losing focus on the central axis of investigation (Corbin & Strauss, 1990).

Moreover, the Strauss and Corbin (1990) paradigmatic model is based on the identification of six elements: causal conditions, context, intervening

conditions, action/interaction strategies, consequences, the core phenomenon, and the relationships between them. According to Strauss and Corbin (1990), the application of this model enables researchers to systematically think about the data and organize them coherently.

In this research, semi-structured interviews were conducted to collect data from 15 accounting experts in both academic and executive sectors. The participants were selected through snowball sampling (in the first step) and purposive sampling (in the second step) until theoretical saturation was achieved. The obtained data were then coded based on the theoretical coding process, which includes open, axial, and selective coding, following the foundational data theory paradigm of Strauss and Corbin (1990). This process aimed to discover subcategories and main concepts and, ultimately, to develop a structural model of the factors influencing risk appetite in the banks listed on the stock exchange.

The qualitative findings and the constructed model will be validated using credibility methods, including repeatability through a high coefficient of 0.8 and transferability through a systematic and comprehensive theoretical sampling method. The list of interviewees for the qualitative research is presented in Table 1.

In the second part we used the distribution of questionnaires and asked the opinions of about 385 experts in the field of bank risk management to validate the model obtained based on the grounded theory paradigm. For this purpose, after collecting opinions, we validated the model using structural equation model and SmartPLS statistical software. If the path coefficient for each component is greater than 0.3 and the t-statistic is significant, then the component is retained, otherwise it is removed from the model.

Table 1: List of Interviewees for Qualitative Research in the Foundational Data Theory Model

Row	Gender	Education	Experience	Occupation	Field of Study
1	Male	PhD	Over 30 years	University Professor and Faculty Member - Certified Accountant - Member of the Technical and Legal Committee of the Audit Institution Mofid Rahbar	Accounting
2	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	University Professor and Director and Partner of the Audit and Certified Accountant Institution	Accounting
3	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	Manager of the Risk Department of Bank Melli	Accounting
4	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	Director and Partner of the Audit Institution and Member of the Insurance and Banking Task Force	Accounting
5	Male	PhD	Over 10 years	University Professor and Faculty Member	Accounting
6	Male	PhD	Over 40 years	Director and Partner of the Audit Institution and Member of the Insurance and Banking Task Force	Accounting
7	Male	PhD	Over 30 years	University Professor and Faculty Member - Certified Accountant	Accounting
8	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	Manager of the Risk Department of Bank Tejarat	Accounting
9	Male	PhD	Over 30 years	University Professor and Faculty Member - Certified Accountant	Accounting
10	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	Director and Partner of the Audit and Certified Accountant Institution	Accounting
11	Male	PhD	Over 15 years	Faculty Member, Certified Financial Accountant, Official Expert of the Judiciary	Accounting
12	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	Manager of the Risk Department of Bank Melli	Accounting
13	Male	PhD	Over 20 years	Director and Partner of the Audit Institution and Member of the Insurance and Banking Task Force	Accounting
14	Female	PhD	Over 10 years	University Professor and Faculty Member	Accounting
15	Male	PhD	Over 15 years	Director and Partner of the Audit Institution and Certified Accountant	Accounting

4. Findings

To collect data for this study, qualitative interviews were conducted. All interviews were recorded, and audio files were fully implemented. While theoretical saturation was achieved in the last two interviews, additional interviews were conducted to ensure data adequacy. In each interview, the research purpose and the interview process were explained to the interviewee. Both closed and open-ended questions were used to extract the desired information. The aim was to have interviewees narrate all components of the foundational data theory approach in the pattern of risk appetite in banks comprehensively. The analysis of these samples was conducted step by step after each interview concluded. After transcription, key points and concepts were gradually extracted.

Furthermore, the coding process involved identifying speech evidence, conceptual elaboration (code extraction), conceptualization (central coding), and identifying the overall research model (selective coding). Speech evidence or key points are small events with independent meaningful content. Conceptual elaboration, referred to as coding, was applied in this research under the name of codes. After identifying and naming existing concepts, similar concepts were categorized under sub-themes and specific themes. It should be noted that a theme must be more abstract than other concepts. The naming of sub-themes in this research is also more abstract than the concepts that make up each sub-theme. This process was followed for sub-themes.

4.1 Stage One: Open Coding

In open coding, each interview was read multiple times, and after marking and breaking down the data, any concept that came to mind was considered. There was no limit to naming concepts in this stage, resulting in a large number of codes. However, due to the repetitive nature of the information, these codes decreased over time. Similar concepts were identified in this stage, and under the title of sub-themes and specific themes, they were classified. It is important to note that a theme should be more abstract than other concepts (Gharekhani, 2017). The names chosen for sub-themes in this research are also more abstract than the concepts that make up each sub-theme. This process was followed for sub-themes.

4.1.1 Data Analysis and Model Formation

Data obtained from the interviews were carefully studied, examined, and analyzed. Similar data were assigned corresponding concepts, and thus, all themes and concepts were extracted and identified. In total, 13 themes and 100 concepts were identified, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Extracted Concepts and Themes from Data Coding

Row	Category	Concept
1	Organizational Maturity	Capital Adequacy Ratio
		NPL Index
		LCR Index
		Ratio of the top 100 borrower's facilities to total loans
		Ratio of the top 100 depositor's deposits to total deposits
		Ratio of facilities for 20 beneficiaries to total facilities
		Organizational culture
		Regulatory bodies
		Competitors
		Interest rate level
2	Organizational Factors	Customer acquisition and marketing approach
		Workflow processes
		Level of commitment and acceptance of risk appetite in each organization
		Access to appropriate financial resources portfolio
		Customer diversity
		Access and facilities
		Banks' risk capacity
		External factors
		Liquidity status
		Economic factors
3	Appropriate Risk Approaches	Risk-taking approach of the board of directors
		Risk-averse approach of the board of directors
		Bank's own plans
		Central bank regulations on risks
		Non-performing claims risk
4	Management Methods	Management methods in banks
		Decision-making structure in banks
		Independence of banks in decision-making, independent of external factors
		Independence of banks in planning, independent of external factors
		Determining risk appetites
5	Risk Situation	Determining risk tolerance in key bank risk indicators
		Current risk situation
		Acceptable risk situation
		Importance for capital
		Organization management by senior management
		Costs resulting from risk

Row	Category	Concept
1	Organizational Maturity	Capital Adequacy Ratio
6	Expansion and Communication Framework	Internal credit scoring system
		Stakeholder and related person system
		Documentation and guarantees system
		Asset and liabilities management system (resources and knowledge)
		Current status
		Laws and regulations
		Organizational structure
		Internal control structure
		Decision-making committees
		Bank's goals and strategies
7	Improving Risk Appetite Framework	Corporate governance culture
		Existence of information infrastructure
		Resource growth
		Having a strategic plan
		Defining the main and sub-goals of the organization
		Identifying the risks of the main and sub-goals of the organization
		Understanding risk calculation methods
8	Regulatory Expectations	Interaction with the central bank's check and commitments system for obtaining records of bounced checks and customer facilities and commitments
		Understanding the organization's risk capacity before shaping the strategy and setting risk appetites
		Bank's compliance with laws and regulations
		Investment in strong infrastructure to support banking business
		Existence of an effective risk appetite framework
		Strong and active interaction by the board of directors and senior management
		Strong internal relationships within the company
9	Risk Monitoring and Feedback Strategies	High responsibility of senior management for risk appetites
		Self-risk assessment and control
		Monitoring the bank's risk within the risk appetite framework
		Existence of regulatory bodies
		Existence of qualitative statements and risk criteria
		Strengthening information technology and data infrastructure
10	Risks Related to Banks	Risks related to the economic environment
		Risks related to the social environment
		Risks related to the political environment
		Sanctions
		Economic recession
		Determining the directive interest rate

Row	Category	Concept
1	Organizational Maturity	Capital Adequacy Ratio
11	Laws and Regulations	Determining the directive banking interest rate Exchange rate fluctuations Economic prosperity Gross national product Constant changes in laws and regulations Employee support Managers' lack of awareness of risks
12	Continuity of Activity	Improving risk management processes in banks Risk appetite planning for each risk Identifying markets Need for communication between units Interconnectivity of various bank units Preparation of comprehensive policies Unified risk management
13	Organizational Excellence	Environmental factors Income stability Profit stability Performance stability Increase in bank credit rating Facilities and facilitation Increased efficiency Increased effectiveness Non-waste of employees' time Responsiveness to available resources Organization survival Cost savings Continuous growth of banks and confidence in system control

4.2 Stage Two: Central Coding

In central coding and selection, the extracted concepts from open coding are classified into six categories, including central concept, causal conditions, intervening conditions, contextual conditions, strategies (actions and reactions), and consequences, based on the systematic paradigm theory of Strauss and Corbin (1990).

4.3 Stage Three: Selective Coding and Theory Building

As mentioned earlier, grounded theory is a qualitative research method derived from theory development based on data (grounded theory). It emerged as an alternative strategy to traditional approaches in scientific research, which heavily relied on hypothesis testing and confirmation,

verification techniques, and quantitative analytical methods. In the current research, aiming to "develop a structural model of factors affecting risk appetites in banks accepted in the stock market," the researcher dedicated all efforts to using a systematic set of qualitative techniques (based on grounded theory) for an inductive approach to formulate a theory regarding the factors influencing risk appetites in banks (Gong et al., 2021).

Importantly, the researcher applied various strategies to balance creativity and science in developing a systematic theory, including (1) iterative backward reviewing and questioning, (2) adopting a skeptical attitude, and so on.

The model described in the text demonstrates how specific factors and conditions interact with each other, leading to the emergence of a structural pattern of native factors influencing risk appetites in banks accepted in the stock market. These factors can be broadly categorized into organizational maturity and organizational factors. Additionally, the model shows that the occurrence of these factors takes place within a specific framework that significantly influences the model of factors influencing risk appetites in banks. Among these influential factors, the expansion and communication framework are highlighted (Hasan et al., 2022).

Purposeful actions and reactions to specific issues can lead to the development and utilization of the studied pattern. This includes categories such as risk management status, improvement of risk appetite framework, appropriate risk approaches, risks related to banks, laws and regulations, and regulatory expectations.

It is evident that attention to factors such as organizational maturity and organizational factors is crucial for policymaking regarding factors influencing risk appetites in banks. In the next step, other parameters and factors need to be carefully considered, as they are equally important and provide the necessary context for an effective process. The occurrence of these events will be guided and controlled through managerial strategies in directing and controlling the central monitoring and feedback phenomenon. Ultimately, the achieved results include the consequences of organizational continuity and excellence.

Therefore, selective coding is a crucial stage in grounded theory development that, based on the results of axial and central coding, leads to the formulation of a theory. Selective coding is the process of integration, improvement, and refinement of concepts to organize them systematically for the presentation and shaping of a theory. At this level, an attempt is made to create a systematic relationship between concepts around the central concept as the main theme, presenting a theoretical narrative for the phenomenon. The results of data analysis indicate that managerial approaches and risk status can accurately evaluate, measure, and determine the appropriate level of behavioral accounting management, ultimately managing the situation of factors influencing risk appetites in banks. The results of selective coding have led to the extraction of a proposed model, and based on these explanations, the model of selective coding and theory creation is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Structural Model of Factors Influencing Risk Appetite in Accepted Banks on the Stock Exchange Based on the Grounded Theory Paradigm

5. Model validation

It should be noted that in this section, a questionnaire based on the indicators, components, concepts and categories of the proposed model has been prepared, and this questionnaire (Likert scale) includes 100 questions about the dimensions and components in the model based on the grounded theory paradigm. After testing questionnaire validity (based on the opinion of experts and specialists) and reliability (according to Cronbach's alpha, 78% is more than the corresponding sample (70%)), 385 questionnaires were collected to do the analysis. To do the data analysis we used structural equation modeling method and SmartPLS software. The standardized estimation output of the structural equation model is shown for the conceptual model of the research.

According to the results presented in Table 3 to 8 we find that our model is valid. Because all path coefficients are greater than 0.3 and t statistics are greater than 1.96. Therefore, Validation tests show that all components of our model based on grounded theory paradigm are significant and we can generalize our findings to the society. Details of tests outputs are given in Table 3 and 4.

Table 3: Test of existing structural relationships related to the variable of causal conditions in the final model

Model Elements	Components	Subcomponents	Path Coefficient	t	Result
conditions Causal	Organizational maturity	Capital adequacy ratio	0.46	3.00	Not Rejected
		NPL index	0.42	5.37	Not Rejected
		LCR index	0.49	5.87	Not Rejected
		The ratio of the 100 largest bank receiver facilities to the total facilities	0.43	5.94	Not Rejected
		The ratio of the 100 largest bank depositors to total deposits	0.42	5.48	Not Rejected
		The ratio of the facilities of 20 single beneficiaries to the total facilities	0.54	5.74	Not Rejected

Model Elements	Components	Subcomponents	Path Coefficient	t	Result
		Organizational culture	0.51	6.17	Not Rejected
		Regulatory bodies	0.42	6.6	Not Rejected
		Competitors	0.51	6.15	Not Rejected
		Interest rate	0.5	6.24	Not Rejected
		How to attract customers and marketing	0.43	4.96	Not Rejected
	maturity Organizational	Capital adequacy ratio	0.63	3.00	Not Rejected
		NPL index	0.52	9.28	Not Rejected
		LCR index	0.47	9.80	Not Rejected
		The ratio of the 100 largest bank receiver facilities to the total facilities	0.44	7.83	Not Rejected
		The ratio of the 100 largest bank depositors to total deposits	0.42	7.90	Not Rejected
		The ratio of the facilities of 20 single beneficiaries to the total facilities	0.42	8.53	Not Rejected
		Organizational culture	0.47	8.91	Not Rejected
		Regulatory bodies	0.48	7.68	Not Rejected
		Competitors	0.51	9.34	Not Rejected
		Appropriate risk approaches	Risk taking approach of the board of directors	0.48	3.00
	Risk-averse approach of the board of directors		0.58	9.92	Not Rejected
	Banks' own programs		0.54	9.14	Not Rejected
	The rules and regulations of the Central Bank regarding risks		0.61	10.29	Not Rejected
	Risk of non-collection of claims		0.62	10.05	Not Rejected

Table 4 Test of existing structural relationships related to the variable of The Contextual conditions in the final model

Model Elements	Components	Subcomponents	Path Coefficient	t	Result
The central Phenomenon	Management practices	Management method in banks	0.57	8.57	Not Rejected
		Decision making structure in banks	0.57	10.36	Not Rejected
		The independence of banks in making decisions more independent from external factors	0.59	9.91	Not Rejected
		Independence of banks in planning, more independent from external factors	0.64	10.13	Not Rejected
		Determining risk appetite	0.48	8.76	Not Rejected
		Determining risk tolerance in the main bank risk indicators	0.49	7.61	Not Rejected
	Risk status	Existing risk status	0.41	7.41	Not Rejected
		Acceptable risk status	0.48	7.30	Not Rejected
		Importance for capital	0.43	6.83	Not Rejected
		Management of the organization by senior management	0.64	7.93	Not Rejected
		Costs due to risk	0.55	7.70	Not Rejected

6. Discussion

The present research aimed to develop and validate a structural model of factors influencing risk appetite in banks accepted on the stock exchange based on the Grounded Theory paradigm. The research progressed through stages, following the steps of grounded theory data-driven theory

development. The literature review and interviews with 15 experts in the field contributed to the identification of 100 concepts and 13 categories.

The central category identified in this study is "Supervision and Feedback on Risk Strategy," around which 12 other categories revolve, forming the elements of the grounded theory derived from the research. These categories are classified into six groups: Causal Conditions (2 categories), Strategies (1 category), Context or Background (1 category), Intervention Conditions (6 categories), and Consequences (2 categories).

Causal Conditions: Two categories, "Organizational Maturity and Organizational Factors," are considered as causal conditions. Organizational maturity includes factors such as capital adequacy ratio, NPL index, LCR index, the ratio of large borrowers to total facilities, and more, as identified in Table 2. Organizational factors include processes, commitment levels, and acceptance within each organization regarding risk appetite, access to suitable financial resources, and more.

Intervention or Mediating Conditions (General Conditions): Among other categories, six categories, including "Appropriate Risk Approaches, Improvement of Risk Appetite Framework, Risk Status, Risks Related to Banks, Regulations and Laws; Supervisory Expectations," are considered as general intervention conditions that either limit or facilitate action and interaction.

1. Risks Related to Banks encompass risks related to the economic, social, political environment, sanctions, economic downturns, and determination of the interest rate policy.
2. Regulations and Laws include concepts such as determining the interest rate policy, exchange rate fluctuations, economic prosperity, gross national product, and more.
3. Supervisory Expectations include concepts related to interaction with the check system and central bank commitments to obtain the records of bounced checks and facilities and customer commitments, understanding the organization's risk capacity before forming a strategy, and regulating risk appetite.

4. Improvement of Risk Appetite Framework includes concepts related to corporate governance culture, information infrastructure, resource growth, having a strategic plan, defining the organization's main and subsidiary goals, determining risk objectives, and recognizing risk calculation methods.
5. Risk Status includes the current risk status, acceptable risk status, importance to capital, organizational management by senior management, and costs arising from risk.
6. Appropriate Risk Approaches include risk-tolerant and risk-averse approaches by the board of directors, banks' own plans, central bank regulations on risks, and the risk of non-recovery of claims.

The results of this qualitative study align with the findings of several prior research studies, including those by Gharakhani (2017), Sadeghi and Sadeghi (2016), Mio et al. (2022), and Mare (2019). These studies collectively emphasize the importance of possessing and presenting a risk appetite framework as a tool for determining risk tolerance limits, preventing the bankruptcy of companies and financial institutions.

The study also resonates with the insights from ISO Guide 73 (2009), which emphasizes that the organizational approach to risk significantly affects risk inclination and tolerance levels. The research reinforces the notion that the effective management of risk involves a cohesive set of strategies aimed at balancing returns and associated risks, utilizing organizational resources efficiently, and achieving organizational goals.

7. Conclusion

This study designed and validated a structural model of the factors influencing risk appetite in banks listed on the stock exchange, employing the Grounded Theory Paradigm. The research, through a series of semi-structured interviews with accounting experts, uncovered critical causal, intervening, and outcome-related factors impacting risk appetite. The study highlights the importance of organizational maturity, communication expansion, and robust risk management strategies as key drivers in maintaining organizational continuity and growth, particularly

in the face of financial instability and market uncertainties. The model was further validated using confirmatory and discriminant analysis methods, reinforcing the reliability and applicability of the findings to the banking sector.

The implications of this research are twofold. First, it emphasizes the necessity for banks to adopt a more integrated approach to risk management that aligns risk appetite with organizational goals and market conditions. Second, the model offers a practical framework that can guide banks in improving their risk assessment processes and risk appetite documentation, ultimately leading to better risk mitigation and organizational performance. Future research can expand upon these findings by applying the model to other financial institutions and exploring its applicability in different market environments.

Overall, this study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on risk management in the banking sector and provides actionable insights for practitioners and policymakers striving to optimize risk appetite frameworks in today's dynamic financial landscape.

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